

Field study on night-time driver reaction times under different road lighting.

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ABSTRACT

Traffic safety remains a critical concern globally, necessitating urgent measures to reduce crash risks and road accidents. Night-time driving poses the highest risks, with road lighting employed to enhance visibility, especially in high-conflict areas such as roundabouts and pedestrian crossings. This field study introduces a novel method to accurately measure drivers' reaction times under conditions resembling real-life nighttime driving on illuminated roads. Three different road lighting settings were tested: class C5 and C2 with constant output, and class C5 with 90 Hz modulated output. Participants drove back and forth along the test track at a moderate speed (around 30 km/h) and were instructed to brake distinctly as quickly as possible when a target appeared on the side of the road. The test was conducted at night-time in winter road conditions. Reaction times were measured for both the release of the gas pedal (perception time) and the pressing of the brake pedal in response to the targets. The developed method, which proved to be robust and highly accurate, utilized rotating targets triggered by a passing vehicle, pressure-sensitive sensors on the gas and brake pedals and GPS-synchronized time stamps. Results indicated a significant age-related increase in reaction times, with an increment of 0.002 seconds per year. No significant differences in brake reaction times were observed between male and female drivers, nor among the different lighting settings. Reaction times remained consistent across all lighting conditions, even at the lowest light level. These findings contribute valuable insights to the discussion on the sufficient light levels needed to ensure adequate night-time visibility without compromising traffic safety.

KEYWORDS: Road lighting, reaction time, measurement, field study, luminance, GPS-time, temporal light modulation

1. Introduction

Traffic safety is a global concern. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 1.19 million people are killed and an additional 20-50 million are injured in road traffic accidents each year [1]. Although the number of fatalities has decreased by 5% since 2010, traffic accidents remain the leading cause of death among children and young adults aged 5-29. The WHO reports that pedestrian fatalities increased 3% from 2010 to 2021, and more than half (53%) of all road traffic deaths involve the least protected road users: pedestrians, cyclists, motorcyclists, and e-scooter users. There is an urgent need, both socially and economically, to improve road safety and reduce the number of fatalities and injuries worldwide.

Nighttime poses the highest risk for road traffic accidents. In a study by Wanvik, the risk of injury accidents was found to increase in darkness. The average increase in risk at nighttime compared to daylight was estimated to be 17% on lit rural roads and 145% on unlit rural roads [2]. Furthermore, according to a research note from the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA), the fatality rate per vehicle mile of travel in the US is approximately three times higher at night than during the day [3]. Pedestrians, being the most vulnerable and least visible road user group, face an even greater risk during nighttime. One study found that the average increase in risk with respect to pedestrian accidents was as high as 140% on lit rural roads and about 360% on unlit rural roads [2]. In a study by Flannagan et al., the risk for pedestrian accidents at nighttime was found to be up to seven times higher than during daylight hours [4].

Properly designed and balanced road lighting can improve the visibility of pedestrians and cyclists at night, thus providing a longer recognition distance and a better opportunity for vehicle drivers to react in time to avoid an accident [5]. The importance of road lighting for traffic safety is well known [6], as adequate road lighting enhances the visual performance, visual comfort, and alertness of road users. In a study of crash rates at intersections before and after lighting was installed, a 13% reduction in night crash frequency and a 36% decrease in the ratio of night to day crash rate were observed [7]. Other studies have shown that well-planned lighting can reduce nighttime accidents by more than 30% [2,8,9].

Reaction time, the time taken by a driver to respond to a stimulus, is a crucial factor in ensuring traffic safety. Short reaction times are essential for avoiding collisions [10]. It is an important variable in crash risk analysis and when designing road infrastructure and signaling systems [11-12]. The total reaction time can be divided into the following sequence of components [13]:

1. *Perception time (mental processing time)*: The time it takes for the responder to perceive that a signal has occurred and to decide on a response, e.g., the time interval from the first possible sighting of a hazard or signal to the release of the gas pedal.
2. *Movement time*: The time it takes to perform the programmed response movement, e.g., the time required to lift the foot from the accelerator and touch the brake pedal.

The *brake reaction time* is the sum of the perception time and movement time. Furthermore, the *device response time* is the time it takes to bring a car to a halt after brake engagement. This is mostly dependent on the vehicle (speed, braking system, tires) and road properties. Hence, the *total stopping time* is a summation of the perception time and movement time of the driver, and the device response time.

Numerous studies have investigated the reaction times of drivers, both using driving simulators [14-16] and in the field [17-18]. Most of these studies are conducted in daylight conditions. When driving at night, the visibility of objects is reduced even with road lighting, and veiling luminances can impair vision, particularly for older drivers, which may affect the reaction time. In a study by Wood et al., the recognition distance of an object by the side of the road and the brake response time under different dimming levels of the road lighting were tested in the field. It was observed that the response time was significantly longer when the lighting was dimmed to 25% [19].

Various factors can influence the driver response times. Fatigue, mental and physical distractions, and alcohol consumption are known to increase the reaction time [20-22] while high alertness or anticipation (anticipatory muscle tension) can decrease the mean response time [14]. Flicker, i.e., modulated (blinking) light below the critical fusion threshold, is employed in signaling systems to enhance attention and raise the expectations, thereby reducing the median response time (i.e., fewer long reaction times caused by attentional lapses). Notably, previous studies on the impact of temporal light modulations (TLM) on the human brain have observed increased alertness even when the modulations are not consciously perceived (i.e., above the threshold for flicker perception) [23-24]. Furthermore, using methods like electro-encephalography (EEG) and pupillometry, it has been demonstrated that TLM increase brain activity and physiological arousal when performing visual tasks under light with frequencies around 100 Hz [25-26].

This suggests that it may be possible to increase the alertness of drivers at night without using blinking lights. This approach could be applied at lighted intersections, roundabouts, and other medium-risk conflict areas where blinking lights are not considered warranted.

As LED lighting provide an opportunity to vary and control the lighting by dimming and introducing modulations, this theory could be tested in the current study by measuring the perception time and brake response time of drivers when driving along a road section under modulated and constant road lighting. Furthermore, the influence of light levels on response time when driving on a winter road was tested. Accurate measurements of the driver's reaction times when targets were triggered along the road were made possible by equipping the gas and brake pedals of a car with high-speed switches and recording the times for each event using GPS-synchronized clocks. To the authors' knowledge, the method employed in this study is unique, as it combines a field experiment under realistic conditions with high-accuracy reaction time measurements across different road lighting settings.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Test site and conditions

The field test was set up at the vehicle test facility AstaZero outside Borås, Sweden. AstaZero is full-scale test environment for road safety with a variety of tracks for tests in realistic traffic environments (see www.astazero.com). Asta is short for Active Safety Test Area, and Zero is a reference to the Swedish Parliament's vision for road safety with zero dead and seriously injured in traffic. The tests were performed during three nights in November and December, 2021.

2.1.1. Track

The test was conducted around the FLX Zone at AstaZero, which is designed for vehicle testing and research related to urban areas. The area includes several road intersections and various building blocks such as containers, traffic signs and lane markings, which can be used to create a suitable test

environment. An overview of the FLX Zone and the current test setup is shown in Fig. 1. The main stretch used for the test was a 130 m straight asphalt road with two lanes, illuminated by a total of 14 luminaires, seven on each side of the road. Apart from these luminaires, no other road lighting was present along the test track, which was about 350 m long one-way and included a small roundabout at turning point 2. A building with the control room and other facilities was located beside the track close to turning point 1. Fabric screens were set up along the side of the road to create an environment with façades, giving the impression of a suburban road where pedestrians could be present.

Fig. 1. Aerial photo (©Lantmäteriet) and schematics of the test track at AstaZero. The length of the illuminated part of the road was 130 m while the full one-way distance travelled by the driver was about 350 m, which included a small roundabout for the second turning point (not shown in the picture).

The total width of the 130 m driveway was about 7 m, with each lane separated by movable strips of road markings. Hidden targets, designed to suddenly appear on the side of the road by a fast-turning mechanism, were placed along the track to trigger a brake response from the test driver when they appeared (see section 2.1.3).

2.1.2. Lighting

Along the main 130 m road stretch, modified road lighting LED luminaires (Prisma light Elton M, Prisma Tibro AB) were temporarily erected using concrete fundamentals. The luminaires were placed in a zig-zag pattern on both sides of the road, using 7.5 m high poles and with about 21 m between the luminaires on the same side. One of the primary objectives of the experiment was to investigate if modulated road lighting could be used to increase the alertness of the driver in critical conflict zones. Therefore, the luminaires were set up relatively close together to achieve the high illuminance levels typically used at road crossings with bicycle lanes and pedestrian zebra crossings. In accordance with the requirements of the Swedish Transport Administration [27], the aim was to achieve a road lighting class (see EN 13201-2:2015 [28]) of at least C3, corresponding to an average horizontal illuminance level (E_{avg}) on the road of 15 lx and a uniformity U_0 (E_{min}/E_{avg}) ≥ 0.4 . Additionally, a lower class was included to investigate the possible influence of the general light level on the driver's reaction time. To avoid the risk of having too low illuminance levels in the final installation, the setup was designed based on class C2 ($E_{avg} \geq 20$ lx).

The light output from the 14 luminaires along the road was controlled by a master unit, placed inside the control room, connected to the other luminaires via RS232. Using a mobile application to communicate with the master unit via Bluetooth, the average intensity and modulation frequency for all luminaires could be changed arbitrarily or set to predetermined settings. The modulation was synchronized for all luminaires, and switching between different settings was almost instantaneous and only noticeable as a brief (<0.1 s) flicker. Throughout this study, the following three lighting settings were used:

1. Modulated output (90 Hz, 50% duty-cycle, 100% modulation depth) – 25 lx
2. Constant output – 25 lx
3. Constant output – 10 lx

The illuminance value reported for each setting refers to the horizontal average illuminance at the road surface, as determined beforehand by simulations done with the lighting design software DIALux evo 9.2 (DIAL GmbH) using the actual (measured) light intensity distribution for one of the luminaires. Measurements on site during the test confirmed that the simulated values agreed with the actual values to within 5% as shown in table 1, resulting in class C2 for setting 1 and 2, and class C5 for setting 3. Also, U_0 was calculated to 0.82, thus well above the C-class requirements of 0.4.

Due to limitations in the control of the luminaires (electronics and software), it was not possible to set a truly constant light output. Therefore, the settings referred to as “Constant” are also modulated but with a frequency of 3000 Hz, as shown in Fig. 2. Since this is well beyond the visibility threshold for both flicker and stroboscopic effects [29], the output can still be considered as constant as experienced by humans under current conditions.

Fig. 2. Temporal characteristics for the three lighting settings used.

2.1.3. Reaction targets

Four identical targets (see Fig. 3) resembling a young boy playing with a soccer ball were placed just outside the driveway of the test track, with two targets on each side of the road as illustrated in Fig. 1. Each target was mounted on a rod attached to a stepper motor (ADI Trinamic PD86-3-1180-TMCL) driven by two 12V car batteries. The batteries and the motor were housed in a weather-safe case, providing a solid foundation that allowed for a rapid 90° rotation of the targets, taking about 0.2 seconds to complete. The motor of each target was connected to a laser photoelectric brake beam sensor (retroreflective sensor Datalogic S62-PL-5-B01-PP) positioned 25 m in front of the target. In the default position, each target was rotated parallel to the road to make it less visible to the drivers.

Additionally, during the experiment, the bases of the targets were mostly hidden by snow, further reducing their visibility.

Fig. 3. Reaction target in the default (left) and triggered position (middle), and on the test track in triggered position (right).

When a certain target was set to active from the control room, a car passing the sensor beam caused the target to rotate perpendicular to the road, signaling to the driver to hit the brake pedal. To further improve the visibility of the target and enhance the triggering of a reaction to brake, a piece of fluorescent fabric was attached via a spring to the target, causing a fluttering effect during rotation.

The targets were primarily illuminated by the road lighting, as the car's low beam headlights were adjusted downwards prior to the test. At a distance of 25 meters, the car lamps contributed approximately 10% of the total vertical illuminance at the center of the targets, which ranged from 15 to 20 lux for all targets under lighting settings 1 and 2.

During the experiment, all targets were clearly visible and well illuminated when triggered. However, due to varying weather conditions, with more or less snow on and around the test track, the effective contrast between the targets and the background was changing over and between the nights. For that reason, no specific contrast measures are presented. The test conditions are further described in the following section.

2.1.4. Test conditions

The test was conducted over three consecutive evenings (Tuesday-Thursday) in November/December 2021, starting at least 45 minutes after sunset to ensure that daylight was negligible compared to the car and road lighting. The weather, and consequently the road conditions, varied significantly between the days. Day 2 was particularly notable due to heavy snowfall and wind, resulting in a fully snow-covered track and overall challenging experimental conditions. The weather on days 1 and 3 was similar, with no significant precipitation. The road conditions on days 1 and 3 were reasonably similar, although some snow and sleet remained on the track on day 3. The difference in conditions between days 2 and 3 is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Typical weather and road conditions during day 2 (left) and day 3 (right).

As the track was snow-covered during all test runs on day 2, with increasing amounts later in the evening, it was impossible for the test subjects to identify and stay in the lanes. Instead, most subjects stayed near the middle of the track regardless of the direction they were going. Occasionally, a target would not activate due to a snow-covered sensor, and on a few occasions, targets were blown down by heavy wind. Despite these difficulties, most of the test runs were carried out according to plan, although there were some missed events and other interruptions.

The different conditions are also illustrated by luminance images of the track and surroundings taken each day with a Technoteam LMK 6 Color luminance camera. Fig. 5 shows the difference in measured luminance between day 1 and 2, with the snow cover on day 2 almost tripling the average track luminance compared to day 1.

Fig. 5. Luminance images of the track area from day 1 (left) and day 2 (right). The polygon regions mark the areas used to calculate average luminance values. Note that the linear luminance color scale has been limited to 10 cd/m^2 to visually enhance the resolution for the road luminance.

Luminance images were also taken under the three different lighting settings (see Fig. 6) and complemented by horizontal illuminance measurements at road level using a Hagner S4 photometer. By comparing measured illuminance values at specific positions with the calculated values from DIALux at the same positions, the actual average road illuminance was determined. All results are summarized in Table 1 below.

Fig. 6. Luminance images of the track area from day 3 under lighting settings 1,2 and 3 (from left to right).

Table 1. The average road illuminance, corresponding road lighting class, and average luminance for the different lighting settings and days.

Setting	E_{avg} (lx)	Class*	Luminance (cd/m ²)		
			Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
1 (90 Hz, high)	23.6	C2 ($E_{avg} \geq 20$)	2.4	5.7	2.4
2 (Constant, high)	26.2	C2 ($E_{avg} \geq 20$)	2.6	6.3	2.6
3 (Constant, low)	9.5	C5 ($E_{avg} \geq 7.5$)	1.1	2.2	1.0

*Classes according to Table 2 in EN 13201-2:2015

2.2. Reaction time measurements

Accurate measurements of drivers' reaction times were facilitated by time-stamping the involved critical events (target activation, release of the gas pedal, and pressing of the brake pedal) using two Raspberry Pi 4 (RPI) single-board computers equipped with GPS modules (Adafruit 746 Ultimate GPS Module) and antennas (CTi GPS-TRK/WP Waterproof) for GPS time synchronization. A Linux PPS client for RPi was used for both time synchronization and for detecting and recording the events. The absolute time accuracy of the systems has not been evaluated in detail, but based on specifications of the GPS modules and actual deviations reported by the Linux PPS client, both the long- and short-term performance is likely better than 1 μ s, which is negligible in relation to the reaction times being measured.

Fig. 7. 3D-printed fixtures fitted with tactile switches to be mounted on the gas and brake pedal of a Volvo V90.

One RPi was in the control room with the input pins connected to the stepping motors controlling the targets. When a target was activated by the car passing the appurtenant laser brake beam sensor

system, the signal from the motor was registered by the RPi and the absolute time (Unix epoch time) for the event was recorded to a text file. The second RPi was placed in the car with the input pins connected to tactile switches (Omron B3F-5001, 12x12 mm) fitted on the gas and brake pedals using 3D-printed fixtures, as shown in Fig. 7. Each fixture had between 15 and 18 switches connected in parallel, so that pressing or depressing any switch would trigger an event to be recorded in a separate text file. The text files were stored locally and analyzed together after the experiment. By cross-referencing the time stamp when a target was activated with the recorded time stamps for the release of the gas pedal and the subsequent braking, the drivers' reaction times were determined. Fig. 8 is showing all registered events for one test subject, and an example of the time cross referencing process is shown in Table 2. Due to some false positives (double or multiple registrations of the same event) the event numbers shown in Table 2 does not perfectly match, i.e., the number of recorded events for brake pedal up are not the same as the number of registered events for brake pedal down.

Fig. 8. All recorded events during a full run, which includes a practice run with two targets activated, and 10 activated targets during the sharp run (12 laps). Note that the event numbering has been scaled for better visibility in the diagram.

Table 2. A short excerpt from the data file containing all logged event for the experiment day no. 3. The excerpt includes a series of events used to determine driver reaction times, starting from the time when a target is activated (green), the first following recorded event for when the gas pedal was released (yellow) and the subsequent brake event (orange). The values in the cells correspond to the total number of each event registered since the recording started.

Unix time stamp	Local time	Gas pedal		Brake pedal		Target	
		Down	Up	Down	Up	Triggered	Cleared
1638460527.820146	Thu Dec 2 16:55:27 2021				1176		
1638460539.844976	Thu Dec 2 16:55:39 2021					52	
1638460540.156877	Thu Dec 2 16:55:40 2021		466				
1638460540.198205	Thu Dec 2 16:55:40 2021						155
1638460540.340364	Thu Dec 2 16:55:40 2021			1090			
1638460541.262578	Thu Dec 2 16:55:41 2021	449					

The number of recorded events for the release of the gas pedal related to target activation was significantly fewer than those for pressing the brake pedal. This is not unexpected, as the subjects were driving at low speed without the need to constantly press the gas pedal distinctly. Instead, to maintain the target speed, they had to ease off the gas pedal regularly. However, individual variations were large; some test subjects had almost no recorded events for gas pedal release, while others had most of them. Thus, the subjects' driving styles, including their foot placement on the gas pedal, clearly had a

significant impact on the recorded events. The overall outcomes with respect to successful test runs and registered time events are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Scheduled and successfully carried out test runs with target releases and registered time events. The percentage values in parenthesis are relative to the number of executed events.

Day	Number of target releases		Events detected	
	Planned	Executed	Gas pedal	Brake pedal
1	130	127	84 (66%)	126 (99%)
2	120	106	94 (89%)	105 (99%)
3	150	149	119 (80%)	149 (100%)
All	400	382	297 (78%)	380 (99%)

2.3. Test participants

Over three evenings, a total of 40 research subjects (27 males and 13 females) completed the test. The study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki and was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the Swedish Research Council. Individuals diagnosed with epilepsy or suffering from recurring migraine attacks were excluded from the study. Additionally, only participants with a valid driver's license were eligible as test drivers. Subjects were recruited through advertisements on the Institute's intranet and from personal networks. They ranged in age from 23 to 73 years (mean age 47.7 years) and represented diverse ethnic backgrounds.

2.4. Procedure

The participants were welcomed at the test track in three different time slots each evening. At the start of the session, information about the aim of the study was provided, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Additionally, the participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without giving an explanation. Personal information was anonymized, and the participants received a gift card worth approximately 20 EUR as remuneration. Before the test, the drivers assessed their sleepiness, visual acuity, and reported their driving experience and habits.

To familiarize the drivers with the test vehicle, the track, and the targets, one practice round (one lap in each direction) was conducted. This was followed by six data collection rounds (twelve laps) with six laps in one direction passing targets 1 and 2 and six laps in the other direction, passing targets 3 and 4. A co-driver was present, as required by the test track regulations. The test vehicle was a Volvo V90 with an automatic transmission and LED headlamps. As mentioned earlier, the low beam headlamps were adjusted downwards, and the brake and gas pedals were equipped with pressure-sensitive sensors.

The drivers were instructed to maintain a speed of approximately 30 km/h, except when braking for a released target or turning the car around at the end of the track. They were specifically instructed to distinctly press the brake pedal as soon as they observed one of the targets being released. However, the drivers were unaware of which target, if any, would be activated on each lap, reducing their anticipation. Also, no information about the lighting and different light settings were given to the drivers beforehand. In most cases, the lighting settings were changed when the driver had passed the illuminated segment of the track and no longer had a direct view of the luminaires.

After the test, the participants reassessed their sleepiness and were asked to give a self-rated experience of the traffic situations and lighting settings. The full test, including information, questionnaire, test run, and data collection was approximately one hour.

2.4.1. Targets and lighting settings

The settings for each test run with respect to active targets and applied lighting settings were determined prior to carrying out the experiment. A full test run consisted of one practice round (one lap in each direction) followed by six data collection rounds which also included two laps without any target being activated. These laps (2 and 7) were the same for each subject. Prior to the experiment, a randomization procedure with restrictions was used to determine active targets and lighting settings for each test run. To ensure a balanced design, the following rules were applied:

3. For every odd numbered test run, the targets to be activated each lap was randomly chosen but with the restrictions that the same target could not be selected more than two times in a row, and that each target was selected two or three times.
4. For every even numbered test run, the target activated for each lap was switched compared to the preceding odd run.
5. The lighting settings for each run were decided by sequentially adding randomly selected permutations of 1,2 and 3, thus always ending up with each lighting setting being used four times and never appearing more than two times in a row.
6. The final 40 test run sequences were selected so that all combinations of targets and lighting settings were balanced to within 5%.

2.5. Data analysis

It is known from previous research that the individual perception time distribution function is positively skewed. The lower limit is constrained by the speed of signal transmittance in the brain and neurons, while there is no upper boundary for the long perception time tail [30]. This distribution is often described by an exponentially modified Gaussian (EMG) distribution [30-31].

The measured reaction times (RTs) were first analyzed for outliers. RTs greater than 3 seconds were removed, as a driver would have already passed the moving target before braking. Additionally, RTs less than 0.1 seconds were excluded, due to the perception response time limit described above. The mean and standard deviation (σ) were then calculated for the remaining data, and data points deviating more than 3σ from the mean were excluded. Overall, this procedure resulted in the removal of 5% of the data points from the gas reaction time data set and 3% from the brake reaction time data set.

Several statistical tests were used to analyze the data utilizing OriginLab software (OriginPro 2023, OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA) and MATLAB (R2023b, The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA, USA). Both absolute reaction times, primarily from the more complete brake response time data set, and individual deviations from mean or median values were analyzed depending on the variable of interest. The methods included both parametric (ANOVA) and non-parametric (Kruskal-Wallis) tests, and mixed-effects models (MLMs). The distribution of RTs for different settings and test conditions was modeled using maximum likelihood estimations (MLE) of EMG distributions, performed with the MATLAB script `exgfit` [32].

3. Results

3.1. Data on the drivers

The research subjects had held a driver's license for 5 to 55 years, with a mean of 28.1 years. All participants reported driving regularly in dark conditions and having good eyesight. The annual mileage (in km) reported by the subjects is shown in Fig. 9. On average, male drivers reported a higher annual mileage than the female drivers. Specifically, 56 % of the male participants and 23 % of the female participants reported driving more than 15000 km per year.

Fig. 9. Annual mileage reported by the participants.

3.2. Reaction time distributions

The dataset of the brake reaction times ranging from 0.1 to 2 seconds is shown in Fig. 10. The horizontal dotted line indicates the reaction time corresponding to 3σ (1.28 s), with data points above this threshold being excluded from further analysis. The final data sets consisted of 286 gas reaction times and 372 brake reaction times, with about one-third from female subjects and two-thirds from male subjects. Notably, the data points for day 2 show greater variability compared to days 1 and 3, likely due to poor weather conditions on that day.

Fig. 10. Brake reaction times for all participants and all lighting settings. The vertical dotted horizontal lines separate the data from different test days. The horizontal dotted line indicates the response time corresponding to 3σ (1.28 s).

Furthermore, the brake reaction times on different days were analyzed by fitting an exponentially modified gaussian (EMG) distribution function to the data using maximum likelihood estimation calculations, as shown in Fig. 11. The histograms and the fitted distributions clearly show that the reaction times are skewed, as expected. Although the means and medians differ between the days, these differences are not significant when corrected for the average age of the drivers each day (see section 3.2).

Fig. 11. Normalized histograms of the brake reaction times for the three testing days and the corresponding best fit EMG distribution functions. The Mode is the position of the apex (most probable value) of the EMG. The other parameters describing the function are μ , the mean of the normal distribution, σ , the standard deviation of the normal distribution, and $\tau = 1 / \lambda$, the exponential decay parameter.

3.3. Influence of age, day and sex

The median gas reaction times (perception times) and brake reaction times were calculated for each participant. Fig. 12 illustrates these reaction times as a function of the participant's age, with the sex of each participant also indicated. The data suggest an age-related trend in reaction times, though individual variations are substantial. Additionally, the average movement time, i.e., the difference between the brake and gas reaction times, is relatively constant (mean = 0.182), implying a robust method for the reaction time measurements.

Fig. 12. Individual median gas and brake reaction times as a function of age for male and female participants. The graph indicates an age-related trend in the reaction times.

A linear mixed-effects model, with age as a fixed effect and day as a random effect, confirmed that gas and brake reaction times were age-dependent ($p < 0.002$ for both gas and brake). The gas reaction time increased by 0.0022 s/year, and the brake reaction time increased by 0.0017 s/year. A similar analysis showed that the difference in movement time was not significantly dependent on age.

A Kruskal-Wallis test on the brake reaction times for different days initially indicated a significant difference in the reaction time distributions between days ($p < 0.05$). However, the age distribution varied across the three test days, with more younger drivers on day 3. When correcting for this age dependence, the analysis showed that the differences between days were not significant.

The reaction times were also analyzed for gender differences using Kruskal-Wallis test. For the perception time, i.e., the gas release reaction time, the female participants were significantly faster than the male, although the significance decreased after correcting for the average age (from $p < 0.004$ to $p < 0.04$). However, no significant gender difference was observed for the brake reaction time. This implies that the movement time for male participants should be significantly faster, which was confirmed by another Kruskal-Wallis test ($p < 0.005$).

3.4. Influence of road lighting setting

Almost two-thirds of the participants (63%) reported, after completing the tests, that they had not noticed any difference in lighting settings during driving.

As previously reported, the poor weather conditions and higher road luminance on day 2, compared to day 1 and 3, did not have a significant effect on the reaction time distributions collected on different days. This was further investigated for different lighting settings. The distributions of brake reaction times, grouped by lighting settings is shown in Fig. 13. The data collected on all three days is compared with the data collected on day 1 and day 3 only (excluding day 2).

Fig. 13. Distribution of individual brake reaction times. Day 1, 2 and 3 (left). Day 2 excluded (right).

To reduce the influence of individual variations (including age) and variations in test conditions (such as time of night and weather) the difference between the brake reaction times and the individual median value was calculated for each participant, (n), giving the excess time from median, (Δt):

$$\Delta t_{n,i} = t_{n,i} - \text{median}(t)_n,$$

Where (i) is the lap number, ranging from 1 to 12 in each test run. The distributions of the individual (Δt) for the different lighting settings are shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14. Distributions of excess brake reaction times from individual median, (Δt_n). Day 1, 2 and 3 (left). Day 2 excluded (right).

The distributions of individual excess brake response times per lighting setting are similar whether using data from all three days or excluding the bad weather data from day 2. This similarity justifies including data from all three days in the analysis of the influence of lighting settings on brake reaction times. Fig. 14 also show rather small differences in the group mean or median excess brake reaction times between the lighting settings, and non-significance between the groups was confirmed by both Kruskal-Wallis and ANOVA tests. To further investigate the shape of the distribution of the excess brake reaction times for the different lighting settings, EMG distribution functions were fitted to the datasets (see Fig. 15). Although the fitted distribution for setting 2 is more symmetric than the distributions for setting 1 and 3, the overall difference between the distribution parameters are small.

Fig. 15. Normalized histograms of the excess brake response times from individual median, $\Delta t_{n,i}$, for the three lighting settings with the corresponding best fit EMG distribution functions.

3.5. Influence of lap number and different targets

The distribution ($\Delta t_{n,i}$) across different laps was analyzed using a Kruskal-Wallis test. Significant differences were found between the distributions for laps 1 and 3 compared to laps 10 and 12

($p < 0.002$), with longer reaction times observed in the early laps, possibly indicating a learning effect. Note that no reaction times were collected for lap 2. Despite the four targets used in the test being practically identical, individual variations and differences in surroundings, placement, and target illumination could have influenced the reaction times. Therefore, a linear mixed-effect model was employed, with lap numbers as fixed effects and target number as a random variable. The analysis showed no significant target effect, and ($\Delta t_{n,i}$) was significantly correlated with number ($p < 0.002$, slope = -0.0051 s/lap).

4. Discussion

In line with previous studies, our obtained reaction time distributions were significantly skewed. This necessitates careful analysis of the data and generally avoidance of methods that assume normally distributed data. Outliers were removed in accordance with prior research, though the determination of the upper limit can be debated. An inattentive driver may indeed have a brake reaction time exceeding 3σ from the mean on certain occasions. However, as very few RTs were excluded from the analysis, a different approach to outlier removal will not impact on the results. Additionally, the primary focus of the study was on investigate differences under attentive conditions.

Influence of age and gender: The linear dependence where reaction times increase with age has been found in other studies [16, 33-34]. The influence of gender on reaction time varies between studies [13]. While some studies find that female drivers have longer reaction times than male drivers [16, 35], others argue that there is no physiological reason for this difference. Instead, they suggest it is due to cultural differences and societal expectations regarding physical activity and competitive behavior between men and women [36].

In our study, we did not find any significant difference between the sexes for brake reaction time. However, women had a significantly shorter perception time (gas release), and hence the movement time was shorter for men. Still, the results must be interpreted with care, as the reaction times used in the gender analysis were corrected for age, but different test nights, weather conditions, etc., are confounding factors.

The difference in movement time could also be explained by the fact that the female test participants, on average, reported driving fewer kilometers annually than the male participants. Another possible explanation is that men, with generally larger feet, can place their foot differently on the pedals, resulting in a shorter movement when releasing the gas and pressing the brake pedal. The gender difference in movement time has been observed in another study, with different results depending on the relative placement of the gas and brake pedal [37].

Influence of modulated light: The hypothesis that modulated light would evoke arousal, thereby shortening response time could not be confirmed. Modulated light has previously been shown to increase alertness and shorten reaction times [23-26]. However, these were all controlled laboratory studies, and demonstrating a decrease in reaction time in the field, in a complex situation with more noise, is challenging. The driving task was even more difficult than originally planned due to adverse weather conditions, including wind and snow, especially on day 2. Furthermore, it is possible that the light level was too low and/or that the exposure time was too short to result in a detectable decrease in reaction time.

Influence of light level: The non-significant differences in response to the high and low light level settings indicate that the illuminance on the target is above a certain visibility threshold for all settings. In a previous field study by Wood et al., the reaction time was found to be significantly longer when the lighting was dimmed to 25% compared to the 100% level. However, no significant difference was observed when dimming to 75% and 50% respectively [19]. However, the study by Wood et al. was conducted on dry asphalt in clear weather conditions and is therefore not directly comparable to the current study.

The participants were unaware that different road lighting settings were applied during the test. When asked in the questionnaire after the test run if they noticed that the road lighting was different between laps, 63% had not noticed any change in lighting settings. This was surprising, given that the light level on the targets varied by a factor of about 2.5 between settings 1/2 and 3. The road luminance in front of the car was primarily influenced by the low beam headlights of the test vehicle, which could explain why the different road lighting settings were not noticed by more participants. Still, the facts that no differences in reaction times were observed raises the question of the necessity of the highest road lighting classes. On the other hand, the reaction time is only one factor contributing to traffic safety and additional research, especially in a real-life context, is needed on the subject.

Limitation: There are several limitations in this study. One is that driving on a test track is not the same as driving on a public road. The drivers knew they were monitored and anticipated targets to appear along the road. As there were only two targets per lap, after a few rounds the drivers were aware of the target positions. The measured response times are thus most likely shorter than would be the case if the driver was taken completely by surprise [18]. Another limitation is the different weather conditions, resulting in varying road and background luminances.

Advantages: Our method also offers several advantages. Firstly, the driver does not need to call out or press a button upon seeing a target trigger. Instead, they are just instructed to hit the brakes, a natural response for an experienced driver, when something suddenly appears on the side of the road. Additionally, using an actual test environment with real driving conditions, including a dynamically changing visual environment, provides higher validity to the results compared to using a driving simulator. [38]. The use of GPS-synchronized time stamps proved to be an accurate and robust method of collecting perception time and brake reaction time data.

5. Conclusions

This study presents a field study employing a novel method to accurately measure drivers' reaction times under conditions resembling real-life nighttime driving on illuminated roads. Both the reaction time for releasing the gas pedal (perception time) and the time to press the brake pedal were measured to examine the influence of different road lighting conditions, as well as possible other factors such as sex and age. The method, which involved using rotating targets triggered by a passing car, pressure-sensitive sensors on the gas and brake pedals and recording all relevant events with GPS-synchronized Raspberry Pi devices, proved to be robust. The collected data revealed a clear and significant age-related increase in reaction times, with an increment of 0.002 seconds per year. No significant differences in brake reaction times were found between male and female drivers, nor among the different lighting settings. Reaction times were consistent across all settings, even at the lowest light level. This study brings new insights into the driver reaction times on winter roads in dark conditions. To our knowledge

this is the first study using triggered reaction targets in the field in dark winter conditions, and time stamps for the measurement of gas release and brake reaction times with high accuracy.

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